

Electroprecipitation technology for nutrient recovery: Unlocking wastewater's potential

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ABSTRACT

The reduction of surface water pollution, particularly eutrophication, can be achieved through the extraction and recovery of phosphorus (P) and nitrogen (N) from wastewater (WW). Their reuse supports sustainable agriculture, minimises the depletion of natural resources, and aligns with circular economy principles. In this study, electroprecipitation (EP) was applied to real WW samples collected from three WW treatment plants of different sizes (9000, 40,000, and 150,000 population equivalent (PE)). The influence of reaction time and current density on nutrient recovery was investigated in batch experiments using magnesium anodes, at 22 °C with continuous stirring and a fixed electrode spacing (1 cm), without adjusting pH or electrical conductivity. After EP, the treated effluents were filtered. The liquid phase was analysed for physicochemical parameters, SS, N, P, COD, BOD, metals and *Escherichia coli*, while the precipitate was characterized using FTIR and XRD, pseudo-total metal content, PAHs, and microbiological safety indicators. The results demonstrate that each WW matrix requires tailored treatment conditions: optimal recovery was achieved at 30 min/20 A·m² for WW1, 30 min/10 A·m² for WW2, and 90 min/20 A·m² for WW3. Under these conditions, P removal exceeded 90 %, while N removal ranged from 20 % to 30 %. The resulting precipitates met both EU and Serbian regulations for metal content, confirming their suitability as fertilisers. Treated effluents also complied with EU Regulation 2020/741 for agricultural reuse, with WW2 and WW3 showing broader applicability than WW1. These findings support the potential for implementing electrochemical nutrient recovery at full scale, contributing to circular and sustainable WW management.

1. Introduction

Ammonium and phosphate are vital elements for all living organisms, serving as fundamental building blocks in biological synthesis, including protein formation (Bhoi et al., 2023). The need to preserve these essential resources, to comply with stringent nutrient discharge regulations, and to address the depletion of natural phosphorus reserves has increased interest in recovering nitrogen (N) and phosphorus (P) from wastewater (WW) streams. Recognising WW as a valuable resource has prompted researchers to explore innovative recovery technologies (Soares, 2020).

While N is abundant in the atmosphere, its fixation into usable forms is highly energy-intensive, mainly through the Haber-Bosch

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process. Its removal from WW requires further energy-consuming aeration, accounting for up to 70 % of total energy use at WW treatment plants (WWTPs). In contrast, P is a finite, non-renewable resource primarily sourced from phosphate rock, which is identified by the EU as a critical raw material due to supply risks and growing demand (Daneshgar et al., 2018; Santos et al., 2021).

P consumption has been rising steadily – projected to more than double by 2050 (Nedelciu et al., 2020) – making recovery from secondary sources, like municipal WW, increasingly important. Municipal sewage is the largest source of P losses in the EU (approximately 1.2 g P/person/day), yet its recovery from sludge streams remains underutilised (Muys et al., 2021). Technologies such as chemical and biological precipitation have been widely applied, but they are typically energy- and chemical-intensive (Li et al., 2019; Witek-Krowiak et al., 2022).

Electrochemical precipitation presents notable advantages over traditional chemical precipitation methods for nutrient recovery. Unlike chemical precipitation, which relies on external magnesium salts and pH adjustments (Sousa et al., 2025), electroprecipitation (EP) supplies magnesium ions directly from the anode via anodic dissolution, reducing the need for added chemicals and minimising chemical sludge generation (Campos et al., 2023). This in situ control of Mg^{2+} and pH enhances process efficiency and reduces operational costs (Lei et al., 2018). Chemical precipitation, although well-established and cost-effective, often suffers from high chemical consumption and can produce secondary pollution due to reagent residues (Sousa et al., 2025). In contrast, EP's main energy input is electrical, which offers potential sustainability benefits, especially when coupled with renewable energy sources (Lei et al., 2018). However, EP technology is still emerging and requires further optimisation and scale-up to compete with the simplicity and lower capital cost of chemical methods. Overall, EP offers a promising alternative for WWTPs seeking to integrate circular economy principles by reducing chemical use and improving nutrient recovery efficiency (Campos et al., 2023; Sousa et al., 2025).

Particularly promising is the electrochemical precipitation of struvite ($MgNH_4PO_4 \cdot 6H_2O$), as it enables the simultaneous recovery of P and ammonia without the use of chemical additives. Magnesium ions are released from sacrificial electrodes under an applied current, enabling pH and Mg^{2+} control without dosing reagents. This makes the process more sustainable, and the final product – struvite – a valuable slow-release fertiliser (Metcalf and Eddy, 2003).

The general equation for struvite formation is as follows (Metcalf and Eddy, 2003):

Numerous studies have demonstrated the effectiveness of EP, with phosphate recovery exceeding 90 % in synthetic WW under optimised conditions (Campos et al., 2023; Kékedy-Nagy et al., 2020; Lei et al., 2018; Li et al., 2021; Natsi and Koutsoukos, 2024). For instance, Campos et al., (2023) demonstrated over 90 % phosphate recovery under optimised Mg:N:P ratios and pH control; Kékedy-Nagy et al. (2020) reported a 4.5-fold greater struvite yield using pure Mg anodes in just 6 h, forming crystalline $\sim 30 \mu m$ particles, and Li et al. (2021) achieved 91 % total phosphate removal, with $\sim 41.5 \%$ struvite in the deposit, using 5.76 A/m^2 at pH 8.5. Moreover, Lei et al. (2018) recorded 98 % P removal in 5 min at only 1 mA/cm^2 with minimal energy use ($\sim 0.039 \text{ kWh/m}^3$). Finally, Natsi and Koutsoukos (2024) confirmed spontaneous struvite precipitation and $\sim 20 \mu m$ crystal formation with Mg anodes at low current densities ($\sim 10 \text{ mA/cm}^2$), even without pH adjustment. These concrete efficiencies and crystal confirmations provide strong experimental support for the theoretical claims.

However, a research gap still exists. Most published studies have focused on synthetic WW, which lacks the complexity and variability of real WWTP effluents that may contain competing ions, organic loads, or industrial contributions. In particular, there is limited knowledge about how key operational parameters – such as current density (CD) and reaction time – interact in EP processes using real municipal WW of different origins and scales. Furthermore, comparisons between WWTPs with differing levels of industrial load and population size remain scarce. Addressing these gaps is essential to transition electrochemical recovery methods from lab-scale feasibility to practical, real-world application.

To the best of our knowledge, there is a lack of research investigating the interactions between parameters such as reaction time and CD, which affect the generation of metal ions from the anode. Additionally, studies comparing real samples from WWTPs with varying capacities are also limited (Bhoi et al., 2023; Santos et al., 2024). Considering the interactions between P and N in WW streams can help optimise their recovery while reducing energy consumption. The results of this study may assist WWTPs in meeting effluent discharge standards and generating potential revenue through the commercialisation of recovered struvite. Struvite recovery is generally feasible only at WWTPs with enhanced biological nutrient removal, typically combined with anaerobic sludge digestion (Aguilar-Pozo et al., 2023). While the market value of struvite currently accounts for only a small portion of the total benefit, the primary advantage for plant operators is improved sludge dewatering and reduced maintenance costs, particularly due to the prevention of pipe clogging caused by uncontrolled struvite precipitation. It is recognised that phosphate concentrations exceeding 50 mg P/L are the minimum threshold for economically viable struvite recovery (Aguilar-Pozo et al., 2023).

In Serbia, annual mineral fertiliser consumption exceeds 400,000 tonnes, of which only 35 % is met by domestic production. According to the Sludge Management Programme of the Republic of Serbia (2023–2032), nutrient-rich streams generated after sludge dewatering are typically returned to the plant's inflow. However, from a resource recovery perspective, the programme proposes struvite formation from these streams as a viable option for larger WWTPs (Ministry of Environmental Protection Republic of Serbia, 2023). Therefore, considering the national fertiliser deficit and emerging regulatory support, this is an opportune time to implement nutrient recovery technologies and enable sustainable fertiliser production from WW.

The aim of this study is to evaluate electrochemical struvite precipitation as a sustainable nutrient recovery approach from real effluents collected at three WWTPs of varying capacities and wastewater profiles. The underlying hypothesis is that, under optimised CD and reaction time, electrochemical treatment can achieve efficient and simultaneous recovery of P and ammonium, with WW characteristics significantly influencing both process efficiency and struvite quality. This work is intended to support practical

implementation by testing real-world conditions and contributing to circular economy strategies through resource recovery.

WW samples were collected from three settlements of different sizes (small, medium, and large). The selection of these WWTPs was intentional and based on key criteria to reflect a gradient of population size, treatment capacity, and varying degrees of industrial wastewater influence. This approach was designed to evaluate how different wastewater compositions affect nutrient concentrations – particularly ammonium and phosphate – and to assess the feasibility of nutrient recovery via struvite precipitation under diverse real-world conditions. By including WWTPs with differing levels of complexity and industrial load, the study aims to capture a representative spectrum of operational and compositional conditions commonly found in WW infrastructure, thus enhancing the generalisability and applicability of the research findings. Also, by evaluating the quality of treated effluents, analysing the characteristics of the separated precipitates, and confirming their suitability as potential fertilisers, this research aims to contribute to a circular economy and zero-waste strategies. The study highlights the potential for resource recovery and sustainable management of waste streams through EP.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Samples collection

The selection of collection points was guided by prior research, which emphasised the importance of an adequate initial P concentration for effective struvite precipitation (Aguilar-Pozo et al., 2023; Santos et al., 2021; Santos et al., 2023). Samples were collected from three WWTPs in the Republic of Serbia with treatment capacities of: (1) 9000 population equivalents (PE) (WW1) with a hydraulic capacity of 1725 m³/day. This plant exclusively treats domestic WW, with no industrial contributions; (2) 40,000 PE (WW2) with a hydraulic capacity of 5000 m³/day. The WW mainly comes from households, with a small contribution from industrial WW, primarily from the food industry and small craft workshops; and (3) 150,000 PE (WW3) with a hydraulic capacity of 36,000 m³/day. The WW treated at this facility consists of both domestic and industrial WW, originating from the food and chemical industries as well as small craft workshops. Each WWTP employs activated sludge systems for secondary treatment and anaerobic digestion for sludge management.

At each WWTP, raw WW samples were collected from the return flow (centrate) generated during sludge dewatering – specifically from the dewatering basin – representing the liquid fraction separated from sludge before it re-enters the treatment process. To ensure representative sampling, a 24-hour composite sample was prepared using an automatic sampler that collected WW portions every 30 min. The combined sample reflects the average quality of WW over a full operational cycle and provides a realistic basis for assessing nutrient recovery potential through electrochemical treatment. The samples were centrifuged to separate the supernatant water from the sludge, providing a clear liquid phase and reducing sludge volume, thereby lowering transportation and disposal costs. The resulting effluents were stored at 2 °C until further use. Prior to characterisation, the effluents were filtered using qualitative filters with a pore size of 2–4 µm and homogenised to minimise the influence of suspended solids (SS) during experiments. The initial characterisation of the wastewater samples, conducted in triplicate with mean values and standard deviation, is presented in Table 1. The general characterisation of WW is a crucial step in the design and interpretation of the EP process for struvite formation. Parameters such as pH, concentrations of P, N, and Mg, as well as overall conductivity, Ca content, organic matter, and potentially present heavy metals, directly influence the course and efficiency of the process. For instance, the presence of ions such as Ca²⁺, Fe³⁺,

Table 1
Characterisation of the tested wastewater samples.

Parameter	WW1	WW2	WW3
pH	7.90 ± 0.20	7.86 ± 0.22	7.20 ± 0.17
Ep	1152 ± 51.5	1491 ± 74.6	1012 ± 48.3
Turbidity (FAU)	39 ± 0.90	28 ± 0.78	53 ± 1.26
SS (mg/L)	31 ± 1.15	20 ± 0.83	43 ± 1.69
COD (mgO ₂ /L)	176 ± 6.51	52 ± 1.90	151 ± 6.37
BOD ₅ (mgO ₂ /L)	78.4 ± 1.35	32 ± 0.92	84.81.48
Total N (mg/L)	287.1 ± 14.2	350.1 ± 14.6	736.8 ± 33.5
Total P (mg/L)	79 ± 3.47	67.9 ± 3.10	121 ± 4.99
Mg (mg/L)	43.9 ± 0.85	8.77 ± 0.13	39.6 ± 0.54
Ca (mg/L)	7.75 ± 0.16	3.64 ± 0.09	9.85 ± 0.18
Na (mg/L)	90.2 ± 0.75	284 ± 5.73	101 ± 1.73
K (mg/L)	50.2 ± 0.52	140 ± 1.73	67.4 ± 0.59
Cd (µg/L)	< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
Pb (µg/L)	< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
Hg (µg/L)	< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
As (µg/L)	9.586 ± 0.12	6.789 ± 0.08	11.35 ± 0.12
Cr (µg/L)	1.224 ± 0.01	3.421 ± 0.03	< PQL
Ni (µg/L)	22.6 ± 0.27	5.38 ± 0.06	8.62 ± 0.10
F (µg/L)	33.17 ± 0.35	46.05 ± 0.42	55.64 ± 0.68
Cu (µg/L)	9.105 ± 0.11	< PQL	14.55 ± 0.15
Zn (µg/L)	3.624 ± 0.05	46.82 ± 0.55	53.46 ± 0.49
B (µg/L)	138.5 ± 1.49	771.4 ± 9.11	188.6 ± 1.73

and Al^{3+} may lead to the formation of competing precipitates (e.g., calcium phosphate), thereby reducing the efficiency of struvite formation (Le Corre et al., 2009). Special attention must be paid to the presence of heavy metals (e.g., Cu^{2+} , Zn^{2+} , Ni^{2+}), which can inhibit struvite crystallisation by competitively binding with PO_4^{3-} and Mg^{2+} ions, altering the structure and purity of the precipitate (Bhuiyan et al., 2007; Yetilmezsoy and Sapci-Zengin, 2009). Moreover, certain metals may partially replace Mg^{2+} in the crystal lattice, affecting the morphology and stability of the crystals, and the presence of these elements in the final product may limit its application in agriculture (Bhuiyan et al., 2007; Yetilmezsoy and Sapci-Zengin, 2009).

2.2. Electroprecipitation experiments

A laboratory-scale batch EP experiment was conducted using a 600 mL borosilicate beaker, with an effective working volume of 500 mL. For all treatments conducted in this study, two AZ31B-type Mg electrodes were used, with an effective surface area of approximately 46 cm^2 (precisely 45.9 cm^2). The use of two Mg electrodes in a similar configuration was also reported by Kruk et al. (2014). AZ31B electrodes consist of approximately 97 % Mg, 2.5–3.5 % Al, 0.6–1.4 % Zn, 0.2 % Mn, 0.1 % Si, 0.05 % Cu, 0.04 % Ca, 0.005 % Fe, and 0.005 % Ni. This composition provides good corrosion resistance, stable dissolution, and mechanical reliability during electrochemical operation. Due to these characteristics, AZ31B electrodes are suitable for use in electrocoagulation and P recovery processes in the form of struvite (Li et al., 2022). The electrodes were powered by a direct current (DC) power supply (DF 1730LCD, Wentronic, Germany).

The advantage of Mg electrodes over alternative materials such as Al or Fe has been confirmed in several studies. Kékedy-Nagy et al. (2020) demonstrated that the Mg-Mg electrode configuration achieved the highest P removal efficiency (93.55 %) compared to Mg-Al (57.15 %), Mg-C (87.3 %), and Mg-SS (88.65 %). This high efficiency is attributed to the low standard reduction potential of Mg ($E^\circ = 2.36 \text{ V}$), which enables the spontaneous release of Mg^{2+} ions even without an external current. Unlike Fe and Al electrodes, Mg directly generates Mg^{2+} ions without forming sludge, thus allowing clean and efficient struvite precipitation. Additionally, during operation, the formation of MgO and $\text{Mg}(\text{OH})_2$ layers, along with the occurrence of the negative differential effect, further enhances anodic dissolution and the overall system performance (Cai et al., 2020).

Rajaniemi et al. (2021) and Zaffar et al. (2023) demonstrated high struvite precipitation efficiency at an inter-electrode distance of 0.5 cm, treating synthetic WW and human urine. In contrast, studies using synthetic WW (Wu et al., 2020) and synthetic urine (Govindan et al., 2021) employed a larger electrode spacing of 1.5 cm during struvite recovery. However, as shown by Zaffar et al. (2023), reducing the electrode distance from 1.5 cm to 0.5 cm led to an increase in P recovery efficiency from 53.5 % to 59.8 %. Furthermore, Mores et al. (2025) confirmed that a spacing of 1 cm enables high efficiency of simultaneous P and ammonia recovery

Fig. 1. The experiment setup.

from WW, with over 90 % P removal. These findings are further supported by literature, which indicates that increasing the electrode distance may reduce electrostatic effects and slow the generation of Mg^{2+} and PO_4^{3-} ions (Naje et al., 2016), while also increasing solution resistance, reducing CD, and ultimately lowering precipitation efficiency (Moradi et al., 2021). In line with the above-mentioned data, an inter-electrode distance of 1 cm was selected in this study as a compromise value that ensures satisfactory process efficiency while maintaining stable operating conditions. Additionally, a review of experimental protocols presented by Bagastyo et al. (2022) shows that in most studies, a certain mixing speed was applied to maintain system homogeneity. Specifically, out of nine reviewed studies, five used a stirring speed in the range of 200–300 rpm. Accordingly, and with the aim of ensuring stable conditions throughout the experiment, continuous agitation using a magnetic stirrer at 280 rpm was applied in this study.

All experiments were carried out at a temperature of 22 °C. The experimental setup is illustrated in Fig. 1. All experiments were performed without pH and electrical conductivity adjustment. After each electrochemical treatment, the samples were immediately filtered using a vacuum unit and Whatman filters with a pore size of 0.45 μm to efficiently separate the solid and liquid phases. The filtrate was collected in sterile bottles and stored at 4 °C, while the precipitate was rinsed with deionised water, dried at room temperature, and preserved for further analysis. A similar procedure was applied by Peeva et al. (2020). Following each experiment, the electrodes were cleaned with abrasive paper and immersed in 10 % HCl for 10 min to remove any deposits formed on their surfaces.

The first set of treatments focused on investigating the kinetics of struvite formation in WW. Unlike most previous studies conducted on synthetic matrices (Bhoi et al., 2023; Wang et al., 2019), the use of a real sample enabled a more realistic assessment of system behaviour. Although Bhoi et al. (2023) reported an optimal time of 35 min for maximum struvite yield, the literature indicates that treatment durations in various studies range from 20 min to several hours (Bagastyo et al., 2022). Accordingly, in this study, time intervals of 30, 60, 90, and 120 min were applied in order to monitor the changes in P, N, and Mg content in the tested WW and to identify the optimal treatment duration. Based on a similar experimental setup reported by Kruk et al. (2014), who investigated CD of 11.4 A/m^2 , 22.7 A/m^2 , and 45.4 A/m^2 , the applied CD for this study was set to 25 A/m^2 for the initial treatments. Following the determination of the optimal treatment duration for each WW sample, the effect of varying CD on struvite precipitation was evaluated. For this purpose, CD of 10 A/m^2 , 20 A/m^2 , 25 A/m^2 , and 30 A/m^2 were tested. Additionally, to evaluate the effectiveness of the implemented treatments, the changes in P, N, Mg content in the examined WW were monitored.

Removal efficiencies were calculated according to the equation: $\%Removal = ((c_0 - c_t)/c_0) \times 100$ (1)

Where C_0 is the initial concentration, and C_t is the concentration after-treatment.

Following the selection of the optimal treatments for the examined WW, a comprehensive analysis was conducted to characterise both the treated WW and the precipitates formed during the process.

2.3. Analytical methods

2.3.1. Characterisation of WW samples

All measurements were conducted in triplicate, and mean values with standard deviation are shown. Analytical methods that were used for characterisation of initial samples and after treatment supernatants are as following. SentTix®21 electrode was used to measure the pH (pH meter 340i, WTW). The specific electrical conductivity (EC) was determined with Cond 3210 conductometer and TetraCon electrode. The determination of Kjeldahl N content in water samples is performed according to the EPA 351.3 method (EPA, 1978). The determination of chemical oxygen demand (COD) was conducted following the standard method SRPS ISO 6060:1994 (SRPS, 1994), while biological oxygen demand (BOD) was measured based on the equipment manufacturers' guidelines—Velp Scientifica Italy, Lovibond, and WTW. Determination of suspended solids (SS) content using the gravimetric method is performed in accordance with standard APHA 2540 D (APHA, AWWA, & WEF, 2023) method and turbidity was assessed according to the standard APHA 2130 B method (APHA, AWWA, & WEF, 2018).

The preparation of WW samples for metal analysis (P, Mg, K, Na, Ca, Cd, Pb, As, Cr, Ni, F, Cu, Zn, B) was performed following EPA 3015A Method (US EPA, 2007). The analysis was carried out using Inductively Coupled Plasma-Mass Spectrometry (ICP-MS) and Flame Atomic Absorption Spectrophotometry (FAAS) as outlined by U.S. EPA guidelines (US EPA, 1994; US EPA 2007). Additionally, Hg content in the prepared samples was determined using the hydride technique, in accordance with the SRPS EN 1483:2008 standard (SRPS, 2008a).

The detection of *Escherichia coli* (*E. coli*) was performed using the standard MPN (Most Probable Number) method ISO 9308-2:2012 (ISO, 2012) for water quality assessment.

Statistical analyses were performed using the software PAST 5.1. To conduct the Principal Component Analysis (PCA), a data matrix was constructed to represent the changes in the efficiency of P and N removal in response to variations in CD and reaction time across the three examined WW samples. PCA extracts the main characteristics of the dataset by transforming the original variables into a set of linearly independent principal components through linear transformation. This process reduces data complexity by disregarding less significant components while retaining those that capture the most important aspects of variation within the dataset. By revealing hidden patterns and correlations, PCA offers deeper insight into how operational parameters influence nutrient recovery. Additionally, Pearson's correlation was used to evaluate linear relationships between the analysed parameters, further supporting the interpretation of EP treatment efficiency.

2.3.2. Characterisation of precipitate

Estimating the quantity of struvite that can be extracted from treated WW is crucial and can be theoretically calculated using the following equation:

$$M_s(g) = (c(\text{mol/L}) \times V(\text{L}) \times M(\text{g/mol}))/1 \quad (2)$$

where: M_s – mass of struvite (in grams); C – concentration of the limiting reagent (mol/L), this is the component (Mg , NH_4^+ , or PO_4^{3-}) that is present in the lowest concentration and limits the formation of struvite; V – volume of the wastewater solution (in liters), this is the volume of WW being treated in which struvite will form; M – molar mass of struvite (245.41 g/mol), this is the molecular weight of struvite.

The solid precipitate samples morphology and composition were analysed by Fourier Transform Infrared spectroscopy (FTIR) and X-ray diffraction (XRD) measurements. For XRD data collection a Philips PW1710 automated X-ray powder diffract metre was used. Each sample was scanned within the 2θ range of 0 – 90° . For the FTIR analysis, a Thermo-Nicolet Nexus 670 instrument was used. The spectrum was recorded in the range of 4000 – 600 cm^{-1} in diffuse reflectance mode, with a resolution of 4 cm^{-1} . The determination of N content in solid samples using the Kjeldahl method is performed according to the standard SRPS EN 13342:2008, Section 1–11 (SRPS, 2008b).

The pseudo-total metal content in the precipitate was determined using the EPA 3015A method (US EPA, 2007). The instrumentation for the water samples (see Section 2.3.1.) was also employed for the solid samples.

The preparation of separated precipitates for the determination of polycyclic aromatic hydrocarbons (PAHs) involved ultrasonic extraction (EPA 3550B (US EPA, 1996c)), purification of the extract using silica gel (US EPA 3620B (US EPA, 1996b) and US EPA 3630C (US EPA, 1996c)), evaporation of the extract in a N_2 stream (EPA 3630C (US EPA, 1996a)), and PAH analysis by gas chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry (EPA 8270C (US EPA, 1996d)). The method ISO 11277:2009 (ISO, 2009) was used to determine the granulometric composition.

E. coli, faecal streptococci, sulphite-reducing clostridia, and *Salmonella* counts were determined in precipitate samples. All counts were expressed per gram of dry sample. Counts of *E. coli* were determined according to the standard MPN method ISO 9308-2:2012 (ISO, 2012). Faecal streptococci counts were determined by standard membrane filtration method ISO 7899-2:2000 (ISO, 2000). Sulphite-reducing clostridia enumerated enrichment in a liquid medium according to the standard MPN method ISO 6461-1:1986 (ISO, 1986). *Salmonella* was detected using the direct method outlined by Pant and Mittal (2008). In brief, 1 mL of the adequate sample dilutions were added to five tubes containing buffered peptone water and incubated for 24 h at 37°C . After incubation, the suspension from each tube was streaked onto XLD agar plates using a loop and further incubated for 24 h at 37°C . Potential *Salmonella* colonies were then transferred from the XLD agar to Triple Sugar Iron (TSI) agar and incubated for an additional 24 h at 37°C . TSI tubes exhibiting reactions typical of *Salmonella* were confirmed through biochemical (lysine decarboxylase, urease, indole production, and the Voges-Proskauer) and serological tests. MPN counts were calculated by using McCrady tables based on the number of positive tubes.

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Effect of reaction time on struvite precipitation

Determining the optimal reaction time is necessary because any prolongation of the treatment would cause excessive consumption of energy and electrodes, which would significantly increase the total costs of the procedure (Aguilar-Ascon, 2020; Leovac Mađerak et al., 2024). Fig. 2 shows the percentage of P and N removal at different time intervals in all three investigated WWs. In WW1 already after 30 min the content of P was reduced by 93 %, and after 120 min the percentage of removal was $> 99\%$. After 30 min of EP

Fig. 2. Percentage of P and N removal in different time intervals.

treatment in WW2, the amount of P was 93 % lower compared to the initial concentration, and after 60 min 95 % lower. Furthermore, with the increase in reaction time, the efficiency of P removal increased slightly, reaching ~99 % after 120 min. By applying EP treatment to WW3, 79 % of P was removed after 30 min, and 91 % after 60 min. The values obtained after 90 min and 120 min of the treatments are identical and indicate that the content of P in the remaining supernatants decreased by > 98 %. The percentage of N removal in WW1 and WW2 gradually increased, from 24 % and 31 % after 30 min to ~ 45 % after 120 min of treatment.

In contrast, the WW3 sample exhibited significantly lower N removal rates – only 17 % after 30 min and ~ 23 % after 60 min, with minimal changes observed during prolonged treatment, despite the pH increasing from an initial 7.2–8.15 (30 min) and 8.41 (120 min). These are values generally considered favourable for struvite precipitation (González-Morales et al., 2021; Le Corre et al., 2009). Therefore, pH can no longer be regarded as a limiting factor in the later stages of WW3 treatment. The low and stagnant efficiency most likely results from the more complex chemical composition of the sample, including high concentrations of SS (43 mg/L) and trace elements such as B (188.6 µg/L), Zn (53.46 µg/L), Cu (14.5 µg/L), and Ca (9.85 mg/L). These ions may act competitively or inhibitory towards the key ions required for struvite crystallisation (Mg^{2+} , PO_4^{3-} , NH_4^+), either by forming other precipitates (e.g., calcium phosphate) or by blocking crystal growth surfaces (Mores et al., 2025; Rahman et al., 2014). Based on these observations, it can be concluded that the poor efficiency and stagnation of N removal in WW3 result from a combination of physicochemical barriers within the sample matrix, rather than from pH alone.

Mg concentration in all three WW samples after EP treatment indicated an increase in Mg levels with longer reaction times (Table 2). From these results, it can be concluded that sufficient Mg was leached from the anode after 30 min in WW1 and WW2, and after 90 min in WW3, to facilitate struvite formation. Thus, the reaction times observed are optimal for struvite precipitation through electrochemical treatment. Literature indicates that equal molar concentrations of Mg^{2+} , NH_4^+ and PO_4^{3-} are required for the formation of struvite, even that due to the presence of competing ions such as Ca^{2+} , Na^+ , K^+ , Al^{3+} , Fe^{3+} , the application of a higher concentration of Mg is desirable than stoichiometrically required (Siciliano et al., 2020). The results align with this, as similar or slightly higher concentrations of Mg were detected after the optimal reaction period compared to the initial levels in the tested WW. Additionally, the pH values measured after the optimal reaction time (~ 8.4) further support these findings (Table 2). According to Cai et al. (2020), a pH above 8 enhances struvite precipitation, and Moulessehouli et al. (2017) found that the maximum struvite crystal growth rate of 20 µm/min occurs at a pH of 8.5, closely matching the pH observed in the tested WW. This pH change was also reported by Kékedy-Nagy et al. (2020).

3.2. Influence of current density on struvite precipitation

Numerous studies (Aguilar-Ascon, 2020; Lima, 2023) have identified CD and treatment duration as central parameters in electrochemical nutrient removal. However, their interaction with WW composition has received comparatively less attention. In our study, the objective was not merely to assess general removal efficiency but to define optimal CD tailored to each real WW sample. This approach aimed to balance nutrient recovery with process sustainability, minimising electrode wear, energy use, and unwanted side reactions.

The results (Fig. 3) indicate that increasing CD from 10 to 30 A/m² leads to marginal gains in P and N removal, with stronger improvements observed for P. Notably, despite similar current inputs, distinct removal rates were observed across matrices, highlighting that WW composition governs performance more than electrochemical intensity alone. This is exemplified by the fact that WW3, with the highest initial P concentration, achieved 99 % removal at 30 A/m², while WW2, with 25 % less initial P, reached only 95 %. These variations underline the matrix-specific nature of electrochemical precipitation and the limited applicability of generalized operating conditions. This observation supports the findings of Franco et al. (2017), who demonstrated P removal under varying CD, but our data further emphasise the role of WW complexity, an aspect overlooked in their work. In contrast to Aguilar-Ascon (2020), who reported higher efficiency with higher current over shorter durations, our study demonstrates that in real matrices, such trends are less pronounced and often non-linear.

Table 2
Changes in Mg concentration and pH values during the reaction time.

Treatment	Time (min)	Mg (mg/L)	pH
WW1	0	39.4 ± 0.54	7.91 ± 0.25
	30	50.1 ± 0.51	8.43 ± 0.24
	60	74.2 ± 0.96	9.25 ± 0.31
	90	81.2 ± 0.87	9.55 ± 0.27
	120	98.6 ± 1.09	9.61 ± 0.29
WW2	0	8.77 ± 0.13	7.87 ± 0.26
	30	6.01 ± 0.06	8.42 ± 0.27
	60	27.5 ± 0.35	8.51 ± 0.26
	90	39.8 ± 0.43	8.78 ± 0.24
	120	8.77 ± 0.09	8.82 ± 0.26
WW3	0	23.6 ± 0.21	7.20 ± 0.22
	30	20.3 ± 0.22	8.15 ± 0.27
	60	29.0 ± 0.32	8.32 ± 0.28
	90	28.7 ± 0.30	8.37 ± 0.27
	120	42.7 ± 0.54	8.41 ± 0.25

Fig. 3. Percentage of P and N removal when applying different current intensities.

A particularly interesting outcome relates to N behaviour. Unlike the linear correlation observed in synthetic matrices by [Chen et al. \(2021\)](#), where higher CD led to proportionally greater N removal, our findings showed only modest improvement with increased current. This divergence aligns with [Sousa et al. \(2023\)](#), who noted that results from synthetic systems often fail to translate to real WW due to matrix complexity and competing reactions.

Additionally, as current increased, so did Mg release from sacrificial anodes, consistent with expectations ([Table 3](#)). However, excessive Mg^{2+} in solution may lead to unwanted magnesium phosphate precipitation, diminishing struvite purity and its value as a fertiliser ([Siciliano et al., 2020](#)). This trade-off further highlights the need for careful CD optimization.

Based on the overall results, the most favourable CD were identified as 20 A/m² for WW1 and WW3, and 10 A/m² for WW2. These conditions yielded 92–96 % P removal and 23–30 % N removal with acceptable Mg dynamics, suggesting efficient and selective recovery. Further, molar ratio calculations confirmed that WW1 most closely meets stoichiometric conditions for struvite formation, supporting the conclusion that its precipitate is likely to be the purest.

Ultimately, our findings reinforce the view that electrochemical precipitation is a robust strategy for nutrient recovery, consistent with [Franco et al. \(2017\)](#) and [Santos et al. \(2024\)](#), who reported 80–90 % P and 20–30 % N removal. However, our study demonstrates that real WW matrices demand individualized treatment strategies. This complexity necessitates adaptable process designs but also presents a significant opportunity to implement circular economy principles through targeted, sustainable nutrient recovery.

3.3. Principal component analysis

PCA was applied to assess the impact of crucial parameters on the efficiency of P and N removal through EP treatment, which is essential for struvite formation. PCA reduced the dimensionality of the data set, which included 6 variants in 3 tested WWs, to two principal axes ([Fig. 4](#)). The first principal component explains 45.2 % of the variance in the data, while the second principal component accounts for 35.3 % of the total variance. The graph clearly shows that the P removal efficiency is highly dependent on the current

Table 3
Effect of current strength on Mg concentrations and pH value.

Treatment	Current intensity (A/m ²)	Mg (mg/L)	pH
WW1	0	39.4 ± 0.54	7.91 ± 0.25
	10	36.4 ± 0.32	8.38 ± 0.26
	20	38.5 ± 0.43	8.46 ± 0.25
	25	46.0 ± 0.44	8.52 ± 0.26
	30	54.3 ± 0.42	9.20 ± 0.28
WW2	0	8.77 ± 0.13	7.87 ± 0.26
	10	36.4 ± 0.32	8.29 ± 0.24
	20	38.5 ± 0.36	8.29 ± 0.23
	25	46.0 ± 0.47	8.38 ± 0.25
	30	54.3 ± 0.52	8.36 ± 0.26
WW3	0	23.6 ± 0.21	7.50 ± 0.23
	10	32.7 ± 0.40	7.73 ± 0.19
	20	33.3 ± 0.38	7.97 ± 0.22
	25	33.1 ± 0.34	8.10 ± 0.24
	30	50.2 ± 0.56	8.26 ± 0.26

Fig. 4. Principal component analysis (PCA) biplot.

strength, while a moderate dependence on the reaction time was also observed. On the other hand, the efficiency of N removal is moderately dependent on the applied current strength, and in terms of reaction time there is no significant correlation since the obtained vectors are at right angles. Additionally, sample grouping into two distinct clusters (WW1 vs. WW2 and WW3) can be observed and explained by differences in initial N concentrations. WW1 had significantly higher initial N concentrations, resulting in different removal patterns compared to WW2 and WW3.

In addition to PCA, Pearson’s correlation analysis was conducted to further examine the relationships between key variables (Fig. 5). On the graph, blue represents positive correlations, while red indicates negative correlations. The intensity of the colour and the size of the points indicate the strength of the correlation – larger and more intensely coloured points represent strong correlations, while smaller and lighter-coloured points indicate weaker relationships. The results show a strong positive correlation between applied CD and reaction time with the efficiency of P removal during the EP treatment. This indicates that increasing CD and extending reaction time enhance P removal through EP. Although there is a positive correlation between N removal efficiency and applied CD, it is significantly weaker than in the case of P removal, suggesting that increasing CD only partially contributes to N removal. The extremely weak correlation between reaction time and N removal efficiency indicates that prolonging EP treatment does not significantly improve N removal efficiency. However, a negative correlation is observed between the initial nutrient concentration and N removal efficiency, suggesting that higher initial nutrient concentrations may reduce the efficiency of N removal during EP. The obtained conclusions are consistent with the research findings.

3.4. Evaluation of remaining wastewater quality after treatment

In order to meet the growing demand for freshwater, particularly in agriculture, it is necessary to consider alternative sources such as treated WW (Biswas et al., 2021). However, to ensure its safe application, the quality of treated water must comply with prescribed

Fig. 5. Pearson’s correlation.

sanitary and environmental standards. In this study, the quality of the residual waters after optimised EP treatments was assessed according to the Serbian Regulation on Permissible Quantities of Hazardous and Harmful Substances in Soil and Irrigation Water (Official Gazette RS, No. 23/94) (RS, 1994) and the EU Regulation 2020/741 of the European Parliament on minimum requirements for water reuse (EP, 2020) (Table 4).

According to the national regulation, all three water samples (WW1–WW3) meet the criteria for irrigation. However, in line with the more stringent EU standards, only WW2 and WW3 qualify as Class B, while WW1 fails to meet the requirement regarding BOD levels. This implies that WW1, although potentially safe under national criteria, cannot be used for agricultural purposes under EU regulation without further treatment. This discrepancy highlights the need to harmonise standards and exercise additional caution when implementing water reuse, especially in the context of international compliance and export-oriented agricultural production. Furthermore, although WW2 and WW3 meet the basic microbiological and chemical requirements of Class B, their use should still be limited to crops not in direct contact with water or not intended for human consumption without further processing. In this sense, treated WW2 and WW3 can represent an important resource for sustainable irrigation, but their application must be accompanied by precise monitoring. Also, further optimisation of the WW1 treatment is recommended to enable its safe use in accordance with modern EU norms.

3.5. Precipitate analysis

Based on the achieved removal efficiencies, the optimal conditions for EP treatment were: for WW1 30 min at a CD of 20 A/m²; for WW2 30 min at 10 A/m²; while for (WW3) the optimal time was 90 min with a current of 20 A/m². The precipitates obtained after these treatments were further analysed in order to evaluate the purity of the resulting struvite, i.e. the amount of impurities.

To validate the obtained results, we calculated the theoretical amount of struvite that can be precipitated based on the initial concentrations in the tested wastewater. In this case, since P was present at a lower concentration than N, and that Mg was consistently leached from the anode during the EP treatment, P was identified as the limiting reagent. Its initial concentration was converted to mol/L and used in the calculation according to Eq. 2. We compared the calculated values with the amount of precipitate remaining after the applied treatments and concluded that the precipitate obtained under the optimised EP conditions for WW3 most closely matched the theoretical maximum amount of struvite that could form (Fig. 6). This can be explained by the achieved removal efficiencies as well as the initial concentrations of the key components. More specifically, we can conclude that the amount of precipitate separated increases as the concentrations of P and N in the WW decrease. A similar quantification methodology was employed by Le Corre et al. (2009), who confirmed that struvite precipitation under real conditions is best assessed using molar ratios, taking into account the complexity of the matrix. In contrast to studies conducted on synthetic WW (Rahman et al., 2014), where chemical purity is higher and deviations are minimal, our results confirm that the behaviour of real WW is significantly more complex and difficult to predict.

Additionally, it is important to highlight that all selected treatments were conducted in triplicate to ensure statistical reliability. The measured precipitate mass values for the WW1, WW2, and WW3 samples showed low variability among replicates, as confirmed by the calculated standard deviations: 0.0014 g for WW1, 0.0015 g for WW2, and 0.0025 g for WW3. These low standard deviation values indicate good reproducibility of the experimental procedure and stability of treatment conditions, as well as reliable quantification of the formed precipitate.

3.5.1. FTIR analysis

FTIR provides a spectroscopic "fingerprint" of compounds, enabling the identification of functional groups and confirming the presence of characteristic chemical bonds in the struvite crystal (Herald et al., 2017). In this case, we applied FTIR spectroscopy to

Table 4
Assessment of wastewater quality after optimised treatments.

Parameter	WW1	WW2	WW3	Limit value				
Cd (mg/L)	< PQL	< PQL	< PQL	0.01	*			
Pb (mg/L)	< PQL	< PQL	< PQL	0.1				
Hg (mg/L)	< PQL	< PQL	< PQL	0.001				
As (mg/L)	0.004 ± 0.00006	< PQL	0.007 ± 0.00009	0.05				
Cr (mg/L)	0.005 ± 0.00005	0.006 ± 0.00007	< PQL	0.5				
Ni (mg/L)	0.01 ± 0.00010	< PQL	0.01 ± 0.0001	0.1				
F (mg/L)	< PQL	< PQL	0.05 ± 0.00043	1.5				
Cu (mg/L)	0.01 ± 0.00008	0.03 ± 0.00031	0.008 ± 0.00009	0.1				
Zn (mg/L)	< PQL	0.03 ± 0.00030	0.035 ± 0.00048	1.0				
B (mg/L)	0.124 ± 0.00161	0.59 ± 0.00690	0.112 ± 0.00137	1.0				
<i>E. coli</i> (MPN/100 mL)	40 ± 1.7	0	50 ± 2.0	≤ 10	A	B	C	D
BOD (mg/L)	39 ± 1.1	22 ± 0.7	18 ± 0.5	≤ 10	≤ 10	≤ 100	≤ 1000	≤ 10,000
SS (mg/L)	< 10	< 10	19 ± 0.8	≤ 10	≤ 25	≤ 25	≤ 25	≤ 25
Turbidity (NTU)	2.7 ± 0.1	2.0 ± 0.04	3.9 ± 0.1	≤ 5	≤ 35	≤ 35	≤ 35	≤ 35
					≤ 5	-	-	-

* Rulebook on Permitted Amounts of Hazardous and Harmful Substances in Soil and Irrigation Water (Official Gazette of the RS, 23/94) (RS, 1994).

** Regulation of the European Parliament and the Council on Minimum Requirements for Water Reuse, 2020/741 (EP, 2020).

Fig. 6. Comparison of the theoretical and obtained amount of precipitate.

analyse potential changes in the internal structure of the crystals formed after optimised EP treatments (Fig. 7). In all three precipitates, medium-strong absorption bands were detected with peaks appearing between 3405 and 3440 cm^{-1} . These bands indicate the H-O-H stretching vibration of crystallized water and suggest that water is strongly bound to Mg cations (Chauhan and Joshi, 2014; Heraldry et al., 2017). The presence of water in the tested precipitates is also indicated by medium-intensity bands occurring at 1633.5 – 1645.1 cm^{-1} in the spectrum. These detected bands are associated with H–O–H bending modes of vibrations suggesting the presence of water (Chauhan and Joshi, 2014). In the formed precipitates, strong absorption bands are observed in the range of 1395.2 – 1401.98 cm^{-1} . These bands result from the bending N-H valence vibrations in NH_4^+ . All of the spectra show bands around 1000 cm^{-1} , which confirm the presence of phosphate (Heraldry et al., 2017; Hostert et al., 2020; Moulessehouli et al., 2017). Also, medium absorption bands were observed in the range around 570 cm^{-1} . Specifically, a band was detected at 583.57 cm^{-1} in the precipitate remaining after EP treatment of WW1, at 572.97 cm^{-1} after EP treatment of WW2, and at 579.14 cm^{-1} after EP treatment of WW3. According to the literature, the intensities of the bands around 570 cm^{-1} indicate the phosphate scissoring vibration of PO_4 (Heraldry et al., 2017). Similar conclusions have been published by Yuanquan et al. (2023). Based on all the above, we can conclude that the obtained spectra are consistent with the struvite spectra found in other studies, confirming its presence in the resulting precipitates.

3.5.2. XRD analysis of the precipitate

For the characterisation of the precipitates formed after all three experiments, XRD analysis was conducted (Fig. 8). The

Fig. 7. FTIR analysis of the obtained precipitates.

confirmation of struvite existence in the separated precipitates is based on the location of specific peaks and their intensity, which should match the standard line in the struvite database. By comparing the peaks/spectra of the examined precipitates with the spectrum of standard struvite presented by Lu et al. (2016) and Kékedy-Nagy et al. (2020), it is evident that struvite was identified in each examined precipitate. As by-products of the treatment, halite and sylvite were also identified in all three precipitates, which can be linked to the presence of Na and K in the tested wastewater. Specifically, based on the initial Na and K concentrations in WWs (Table 1), we can assume that the highest percentage of these minerals is represented in the precipitate separated after the EP treatment of WW2. This observation is also confirmed by the obtained diffractogram (Fig. 8). In addition to these minerals, in the precipitates separated after EP treatment of WW1 and WW3, newberite, a magnesium phosphate mineral ($MgHPO_4 \cdot 3H_2O$), was observed. It is stated in the research paper Lu et al. (2016) that its presence is to reduce the efficiency of nitrogen nutrient removal, as it

Fig. 8. XRD analysis of the obtained precipitates.

reduces the amount of available Mg and PO₄ for struvite formation. However, overall, the amount of nitrogen present was significantly higher in WW1 and WW3 (as is characteristic for these wastewaters) compared to phosphorus, and Mg was consistently leached during the treatment. Therefore, we can conclude that the formation of newberite did not have an inhibitory effect on struvite formation. In the diffractogram of the precipitate formed after the EP treatment of WW3, peaks indicating the presence of calcite and hydroxyapatite are also observed. The presence of these minerals suggests a higher presence of Ca in WW3. This statement correlates with the results presented in Table 1, where the largest amounts of Ca are clearly observed in WW3. Aguilar-Pozo et al. (2023) also detected calcite in the separated precipitate. Thus, the presence and amount of other minerals significantly depend on the characteristics of the treated wastewater.

3.5.3. Quality of the separated precipitates – potential use as fertiliser

According to the European Parliament Regulation 2019/1009 (2019) (EP, 2019), which pertains to the rules for placing fertilising products on the market within the EU, standards for the quality of struvite have been established. The regulation defines 17 physicochemical and 5 microbiological parameters that struvite must meet to be used as a fertiliser or a component in N-P-K fertilisers. Additionally, in line with the strategic goals of soil protection policy in the Republic of Serbia, it is necessary to reduce the input of heavy metals into the soil (Kovačević et al., 2022). Therefore, before any potential use of struvite as a fertiliser, it is essential to conduct an analysis of heavy metals and adhere to the maximum allowable concentrations of heavy metals in fertilisers, soil conditioners, and specialty products (Official Gazette of the RS 30/2018 (RS, 2018)). Table 5 presents the physicochemical and microbiological characteristics of the precipitates obtained after optimised EP treatments.

Current regulations require that the phosphorus content in potential struvite must be at least 7 % of dry matter. The measured P content confirms that this requirement is met, as it ranges from 8.5 % to as high as 22 % in the separated precipitates. Regarding total organic carbon (TOC), the content in all three tested precipitates was below 1 %. Since the WW was centrifuged before EP treatment, all macroscopic impurities were removed. The size of the precipitated particles was larger than 100 µm, and the dry matter content exceeded 99 %. One of the main concerns for using struvite as fertiliser is heavy metals, as they can accumulate and potentially pose a risk to animal and human health through the food chain (Li et al., 2019). Most of the analysed metals (Cd, Cr, Hg, Ni, Zn, Pb, As) were below the detection limit of the equipment or were detected in very low concentrations, which is consistent with the results obtained by Sun et al. (2020). The Fe and Al content was not measured because none of the samples showed metal content exceeding 10 % in dry matter (DM). In addition to these metals, analyses of Ca, K, Mg, and Na were also performed. In Table 5, it can be observed that, for example, Ca is the most abundant in the WW3 precipitate, while the highest concentrations of Na and K were detected in the WW2 precipitate. The obtained results are in correlation with the XRD analysis, as well as with the initial concentrations of Ca, K, Mg, and Na in the WW. PAHs were also not detected in the tested precipitates, while the pollutants biuret and perchlorates were not analysed, as

Table 5
Physicochemical and microbiological characteristics of precipitates obtained after optimised EP treatments.

Parameter	Limit value	Remarks	Struvite-WW1	Struvite-WW2	Struvite-WW3
P ₂ O ₅ content	16 % (7 % P)	Minimum	10.44 ± 0.32	21.87 ± 0.64	8.62 ± 0.27
Organic carbon	3 %	Maximum	0.4 ± 0.01	0.3 ± 0.01	0.6 ± 0.01
Macroscopic impurities	5 g/kg	Maximum	/	/	/
DM content	90 %	Minimum	> 99 %±0.62	> 99 %±0.74	> 99 %±0.49
Particle size 1	At least 90 % particles larger than 100 µm		> 100µm ± 0.27	> 100µm ± 0.38	> 100µm ± 0.31
Heavy metals					
Cd	3 mg/kg	If < 5 % P ₂ O ₅	< PQL	2.36 ± 0.02	1.52 ± 0.02
	60 mg/kg	If > 5 % P ₂ O ₅			
Cr (VI) ^a /Total Cr	2 mg/kg/ ^a 500 mg/kg		< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
Hg	1 mg/kg/ ^a 1 mg/kg		< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
Ni	100 mg/kg/ ^a 100 mg/kg		11.7 ± 0.13	8.7 ± 0.08	4.5 ± 0.04
Cu	600 mg/kg		11.5 ± 0.14	4.23 ± 0.04	< PQL
Zn	1500 mg/kg		31.6 ± 0.31	8.7 ± 0.10	18.5 ± 0.25
Pb	120 mg/kg/ ^a 100 mg/kg		< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
Inorganic As	40 mg/kg		< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
Fe + Al content	10 % DM	Maximum	Not measured; but no samples with 10 % DM metal content/Not evaluated; however, no samples contained 10 % dry matter (DM) metal content.		
Other					
Biuret (C ₂ H ₅ N ₃ O ₂)	12 g/kg DM	/			
Perchlorate (ClO ₄)	50 mg/kg DM				
PAH ^a	6 mg/kg DM	Maximum	< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
Biological contaminants					
<i>E. coli</i>	1000 CFU/g fresh mass	Maximum	< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
Enterococceae	1000 CFU/g fresh mass	Maximum	< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
<i>Clostridium perfringens</i>	100 CFU/g fresh mass	Maximum	/		
<i>Ascaris</i> sp. eggs	Absent in 25 g fresh mass				
Sulphite-reducing clostridia (MPN/100 mL)			< PQL	< PQL	< PQL
<i>Salmonella</i> spp	Absent in 25 g fresh mass		0	0	0

^a Sum of naphthalene, acenaphthylene, acenaphthene, fluorene, phenanthrene, anthracene, fluoranthene, pyrene, benzo[a]anthracene, chrysene, benzo[b]fluoranthene, benzo[k]fluoranthene, benzo[a]pyrene, indeno[1,2,3-cd]pyrene, dibenzo[a,h]anthracene and benzo[ghi]perylene.

^a Limit values according to the RS regulations (Official Gazette of the RS 30/2018 (RS, 2018)).

there is no evidence in the literature suggesting that these substances pose a risk in struvite (Muys et al., 2021). Muys et al. (2021) state that the crystallisation of struvite itself excludes pathogens, leaving them in the aqueous phase, or they are killed during the process due to the elevated pH levels. Additionally, the use of direct current causes the rupture of the membranes of pathogenic microorganisms, leading to their death (Leovac Mađerak et al., 2024). In line with this, pathogens and microbiological parameters such as *E. coli*, total coliform bacteria, enterococci, sulphate-reducing clostridia, and *Salmonella* were not detected in the obtained precipitates. (Sulphate-reducing clostridia are considered an indirect indicator of the presence of *Clostridium perfringens* and *Ascaris* sp. eggs (Muys et al., 2021)).

The quality assessment performed indicates that, in terms of all parameters, the obtained precipitates meet the requirements of the European Parliament Regulation. There is a real possibility of their use either as fertilisers or as component materials in N-P-K fertilisers. Additionally, according to the Serbian regulations, the obtained precipitates meet the requirements concerning heavy metal content, which allows for their application as soil conditioners.

3.5.4. Presence of the main struvite constituents (P, N, Mg, K) in the isolated precipitates

N, P, and K are three essential macronutrients for agricultural productivity (Fang et al., 2023; Khalofah et al., 2022). Due to this, the most important minerals in struvite are P and N, but also K and Mg. When used as a fertiliser, struvite can help regulate the release of nutrients, minimise nutrient losses, and promote sustainable plant growth. This makes it an ideal option for lawns and forests, where fertilisers are typically applied once every few years (Li et al., 2019). According to Sun et al. (2020) and Muys et al. (2021), theoretically pure struvite contains 10 % Mg, 12.6 % P, and 5.7 % N. In Table 6, the percentage content of Mg, N, P, and K in the obtained precipitates is shown. Based on the presented values, it can be observed that the largest deviations from theoretical values are seen in the WW2 precipitate, which contains more than 20 % Mg, P, and also K. In general, compared to available data and previous research (Muys et al., 2021), much higher K content was found in these precipitates. In the other two precipitates, the amounts of P, N, and Mg are much closer to the theoretical values, with K content ranging from 5 % to 7 %. These macronutrients are present to a much lesser extent in organic fertilisers (such as compost or sewage sludge). In general, Erdal et al. (2024) showed that such high amounts of beneficial components can indeed compete with commercial fertilisers like DAP (di-ammonium phosphate), MAP (monoammonium phosphate), TSP (triple superphosphate), and 20–20–20 (NPK fertiliser), regardless of the various produced molar ratios. The study concluded that struvite contributed to the nutrition of P, but also other nutrients (Mg, N, and K), demonstrating superiority over chemical fertilisers.

3.6. Estimation of electricity costs and economic feasibility of the treatment

Understanding the economic and energy aspects of electrochemical WW treatment is crucial for evaluating its practical applicability, especially within the context of the circular economy and sustainable nutrient management (Kékedy-Nagy et al., 2020). Wang et al. (2020) point out that energy demands are one of the main obstacles to implementation, but electrochemical systems often demonstrate both economic and environmental advantages over conventional biological processes. Although the results obtained in this study are preliminary, they provide valuable insight into the potential cost-effectiveness of electrochemical P recovery using Mg electrodes. To calculate the electricity cost, we used the following formula (Eq. (3)):

$$EE \text{ (RSD/m}^3\text{)} = (U \times I \times t \times c) / (V \times 1000) \quad (3)$$

where U – voltage (V), I – current (A), t – treatment time (h), c – electricity price (7.9706 RSD/kWh, green tariff in Serbia – approximately 0.07 €/kWh or \$0.08 USD/kWh), V – volume of treated water (m³), and 1000 is the conversion factor from Wh to kWh. Subsequently, the cost per kilogram of the obtained struvite was calculated as (Eq. (4)):

$$\text{Price per kg of struvite} = EE \text{ (RSD/m}^3\text{)} / \text{struvite yield (kg/m}^3\text{)} \quad (4)$$

The results presented in Table 7 indicate exceptionally low costs of electrochemical treatment, particularly in the case of sample WW2, where the calculated cost per kilogram of recovered struvite was only 0.13 RSD/kg. In general, the recalculated costs per kilogram of recovered struvite from the treated WW are significantly lower than those reported in the literature, where production costs for electrochemically generated struvite range from 63 to 389 RSD/kg (0.54–3.32 €/kg; 0.63–3.89 \$/kg) (Morrissey et al., 2022), further confirming the potential economic competitiveness of the applied method.

However, it is important to emphasise that these results were obtained under controlled laboratory conditions and represent a preliminary estimate that includes only the cost of electricity consumed. Capital expenses (equipment, electrode replacement, labour, maintenance) were not included in the calculation. As pointed out by Magni et al. (2025), a comprehensive assessment of the economic feasibility of such technologies requires a life cycle analysis and cost (LCA and LCC) approach, including sustainability factors, energy requirements, and scalability.

Although the preliminary results suggest high economic viability of the process, validation of these findings will require pilot-scale testing and integration of all operational and capital costs into the final calculation.

3.7. Limitations and future work

The conducted research represents a significant contribution to understanding the potential of electrochemical P recovery from real WW samples using Mg electrodes. The results indicate high process efficiency and a product of satisfactory quality. However, certain

Table 6
Percentage content of the main constituents of struvite in the resulting precipitates.

%	P	N	Mg	K
Theoretical value	12.6	5.7	10	/
Struvite 1	10.4 ± 0.24	4.7 ± 0.14	10.02 ± 0.30	5.07 ± 0.14
Struvite 2	21.9 ± 0.39	5.5 ± 0.15	23.5 ± 0.71	21.9 ± 0.62
Struvite 3	8.62 ± 0.17	7.4 ± 0.23	7.42 ± 0.20	7.7 ± 0.15

Table 7
Cost estimation of treatment and struvite production during electrochemical phosphorus recovery.

Sample	EE (RSD/m ³)	Struvite yield (kg/m ³)	Price		
			(RSD/kg struvite)	(€/kg struvite)	(\$/kg struvite)
WW1	0.32	0.42	0.76	0.007	0.008
WW2	0.080	0.62	0.13	0.001	0.001
WW3	0.76	0.92	0.83	0.007	0.008

limitations of this study should be noted.

The experiments were carried out under laboratory conditions, with the economic feasibility analysis limited solely to electricity consumption costs. Capital expenditures, electrode replacement costs, system maintenance, and human resources were not included in the assessment; therefore, the full economic and environmental justification of the technology can only be established through further research.

The following studies are planned in the next phases:

- Comparison of the obtained struvite with commercially available fertilisers;
- Investigation of nutrient (P and N) release kinetics under conditions relevant to agricultural application;
- Plant trials to evaluate the agronomic efficiency of the product;
- Comprehensive life cycle assessment (LCA), including economic, environmental, and regulatory aspects;
- Process validation at a pilot-scale facility, at a higher technological readiness level.

The implementation of these steps will enable a deeper and more comprehensive evaluation of the sustainability of the proposed technology in the context of the circular economy and efficient nutrient management.

4. Conclusion

This study introduces an innovative application of electrochemical precipitation using Mg electrodes for the simultaneous recovery of P and N from real WW matrices, demonstrating a sustainable alternative to conventional chemical methods. Unlike many previous studies that focused on synthetic WW, our work validates this approach under realistic conditions from three full-scale WWTPs of varying size and composition.

The results confirm that each WW matrix requires tailored EP parameters for optimal performance. Specifically, the highest P removal (> 90 %) was achieved under distinct conditions for each plant: 30 min/20 Am⁻² for WW1, 30 min/10 Am⁻² for WW2, and 90 min/20 Am⁻² for WW3. N removal ranged from 20–30 %. The precipitates (struvite) met EU and Serbian standards for heavy metals, while treated effluents satisfied the reuse criteria under European Regulation 2020/741 – enabling potential agricultural application, except for WW1, which remains suitable for internal recycling. Compared to other studies, our findings are consistent with the high P-removal rates reported in synthetic WW, confirming the feasibility of this method in real matrices. Additionally, the use of PCA analysis and Pearson's correlation results confirm a strong positive relationship between applied CD, reaction time, and P removal efficiency during EP treatment. These findings align with the overall research outcomes, reinforcing the significance of process optimisation in enhancing nutrient recovery. In conclusion, electrochemical precipitation offers a dual benefit: improving effluent quality while recovering valuable nutrients for reuse, advancing both circular economy and zero-waste strategies.

Future work will focus on comprehensive LCA analysis and agronomic validation (e.g., pot trials and germination index) to confirm the environmental and practical performance of recovered struvite. While these activities are time- and resource-intensive, they represent a critical step toward scaling this technology for full implementation in WWTPs.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Nataša Duduković: Writing – original draft, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Nataša Slijepčević:** Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology. **Aleksandra Kulić Mandić:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Vesna Pešić:** Writing – review & editing, Visualization, Methodology. **Anita Leovac Maćerak:** Writing – review & editing. **Đurđa Kerkez:** Writing – review & editing, Project administration.

Ethical Approval

Not applicable

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Data Availability

The datasets generated during and/or analysed during the current study are not publicly available due to authorship reasons but are available from the corresponding author on reasonable request. All authors have read, understood, and have complied as applicable with the statement on "Ethical responsibilities of Authors" as found in the Instructions for Authors and are aware that with minor exceptions, no changes can be made to authorship once the paper is submitted.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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